

LINGUODIDACTIC POTENTIAL OF THE DISCURSIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Maxmudbekova G.U.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17310423>

Relevance: Rethinking approaches and methods of teaching, the object and units of learning

Objective: The objective of this article is to show all aspects of linguodidactic potential in languages

Objectives: to find ways to solve methodological problems related to the qualitative indicator of communicative competence.

In light of new qualitative changes in the system of continuous foreign language education, it is necessary to rethink approaches and methods of teaching, the object and units of learning.

In scientific methodological literature, the unit of foreign language teaching is the text in its linguistic and extralinguistic contexts. Therefore, it can be concluded that discourse, contextually visualized in written and oral communication, becomes one of the components of foreign language teaching content.

From the standpoint of foreign language teaching methods, the discursive approach allows us to take a new look at 1) the components of the content of teaching such as mastery of subject information, the ability to work with texts and the ability to create one's own texts;

2) oral and written discourse as an object and unit of learning, the main categories of which are type and genre; 3) the component composition of communicative competence, reflected in the State Educational Standard as linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competence.

Taking into account the above, it is necessary to note that in the models of communicative competence of foreign countries, discursive competence is separately identified as the ability to perceive and generate texts of various types and genres in accordance with the communicative intention of the speaker or writer within the framework of a specific communication situation.

In this context of learning, five main principles can be identified, which are interpreted as follows:

- Contrastive principle
- Continuity principle
- Derivability principle
- From familiar to unfamiliar principle
- Critical principle

As already noted, discourse is determined by linguistic and extralinguistic content, and therefore, in language teaching, the most significant are the types of speech interaction and various options for realizing the communicative intentions of the interlocutors.

In other words, we are talking about the need to master discursive strategies and tactics to implement successful communication in the context of awareness of the pragmalinguistic features of the construction of discourse and speech acts, as well as the use of means of the category of politeness.

Students must practice producing speech acts and actions depending on the functional palette of speech: informative, modal, expressive, voluntary, and contact-establishing.

Thus, the issues of the discursive approach considered in the article are aimed at finding ways to solve methodological problems associated with the qualitative indicator of foreign language

MPHAPP

THE 6TH INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL
CONFERENCE "MODERN PHARMACEUTICS: ACTUAL
PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS"
TASHKENT, OCTOBER 17, 2025

in-academy.uz

communicative competence and identifying prospects for further research of the discursive approach in linguodidactic terms.